

DEVELOPMENT OF REMOTE BANKING SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IS A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIME

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Annotation

The article examines the increase in capital of commercial banks and the factors influencing it on the basis of theoretical and practical data. Also, based on the study of foreign experience, it is argued that the increase in asset quality in banks will directly improve the quality of credit services provided by banks, reduce problem loans and the use of credit scoring system. A number of specific aspects of the use of credit scoring system in improving the quality of assets of commercial banks have been studied in detail on the basis of theoretical and practical data, scientific proposals and practical recommendations have been developed on the basis of author’s approaches.

Key words:

commercial banks, banking innovations, assets of banks, liabilities of banks, banking operations, deposit, digital technologies, digital economy, banking services, banking products, banking technologies, electronic money, cashless accounts.

1. Introduction.

In order to ensure the financial stability of banks and protect the interests of depositors and creditors, it is necessary to comply with prudential standards set by the Central Bank, and one of these prudential standards is the liquidity ratio, which determines the need to establish a reliable liquidity system in banks [1].

In recent years, constructive measures have been taken in the country to develop the banking system, in particular, the widespread introduction of modern IT technologies in the industry, the acceleration of the digitization process. The process has been accelerated since this year. This is not in vain. As the head of our state noted in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, “Unfortunately, the banking system lags behind modern requirements in the use of digital

technologies, introduction of new banking products and software for 10-15 years [2].

From 2020, each bank will have a large-scale transformation program. In this regard, we will focus on increasing the capital, resource base and income of our banks.” In particular, last year the banking system paid special attention to the establishment of a “project factory” to support entrepreneurs. In turn, the National Bank and Ipoteka Bank are working to issue cheap and long-term resources to banks in international financial markets, for example, by issuing their own Eurobonds. As the head of our state said, “the main goal of banking reform is to train commercial banks to work for customers.”

In this regard, concrete measures are being taken to radically update the software of banks through the widespread use of

information technology, to fully implement the “credit history” information system.

Especially in today’s pandemic, the quality and speed of remote banking services is more important than ever. It is gratifying that in order to prevent the spread of coronavirus disease in our country, positive results are being achieved in the implementation of the process of remote provision of pensions. In particular, significant work is being done to issue plastic cards to retirees. In accordance with this, a number of measures are being taken in our country to improve the quality of remote services provided by commercial banks, to introduce convenient and modern services. Once the epidemiological situation in the republic has stabilized, a citizen (pensioner) can apply to the district (city) branch of the Extrabudgetary Pension Fund and receive a certain part of his / her pension in cash.

At present, there is an appropriate payment infrastructure in all regions for retirees to withdraw cash from ATMs free of charge, as well as to make cashless payments. The ability to make payments online remotely is also a special convenience of using bank cards. In this regard, it is recommended that pensioners who receive their pensions in cash open personal pension-overdraft cards of the Xalq Bank and transfer pension funds to bank cards. This gives them a number of advantages. Plastic cards can be quickly and easily disinfected after calculations. In addition, every bank is now focusing on making payments and banking services remote, that is, easy and convenient to use mobile applications. This means that the use of bank cards is becoming more efficient and convenient than cash.

One of the main risks for banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to improve the quality of credit portfolio and risk management, pursue a moderate growth of lending, pursue a balanced macroeconomic policy, ensure technological stability of the banking system through the implementation of technological solutions for

assessing financial risks liquidity risks will need to be identified and managed early [3].

2. Literature review.

Theoretical, methodological and practical issues of increasing capitalization, managing assets and liabilities of commercial banks were studied in the scientific works of foreign scientists, economists such as E. Gill, T. Koch, E. Reed, X. Grüning, E. Dollan, L. Roger, A. Simanovsky, O. Lavrushin, V. Usoskin, G. Panova, J. Sinki, R. Kotter, W. Soto, Moiseev, E. Zhukova, G. Beloglazova, N. Valentseva, A. Gavrilenko, V. Kolesnikov, G. Korobova, L. Batrakova, A. Litvinova, O. Ovchinnikova, G. Panova, V. Rodionova, I. Rykov, G. Tosunyan and others [4].

Scientific approaches to increasing capitalization, managing assets and liabilities of commercial banks have found practical implementation in the works of local scientists, economists and specialists such as: Sh. Abdullaeva, T. Bobakulov, B. Berdiyarov, T. Karaliev, F. Mullazhanov, A. Omonov, N. Kholmurodov, R. Tajiev, R. Shomurodov, N. Karimov, I. Taimukhamedov, M. Nurmuratov, Z. Kholmakhmadov and many others.

Capitalization is largely determined by economic growth and the global competitiveness of the national economy, while capital is a relatively constant value. That is why the Basel II and Basel III standards made an attempt to bring the technique of implementing the concept of regulatory capital to a qualitatively new level: the level of market-oriented assessments, since the Basel I standard proceeded from the concept of regulatory capital and determined the requirements for capital without taking into account banks real need for it [5].

The analysis of this problem revealed the lack of comprehensive studies on the issue of capitalization of commercial banks in Uzbekistan. There are no clearly developed and used in practice measures on this topic. The very

concept of capitalization is still not associated with the market interpretation of this term in relation to domestic credit institutions. Until now, both in the scientific community and the banking community, capitalization is understood only as an increase in the bank's own capital. For example, Peter S. Rose notes that “we often use the term capitalization, meaning by this own funds or equity capital of banks and its sufficiency to cover risks” [6].

According to our local scientist R. Shomurodov, an expert on monetary policy: The results of a study of the financial and banking system of developed and developing countries show that the capitalization of commercial banks directly affects the development and stability of the country's economy. Bank loans also support the development of small and medium-sized businesses, private entrepreneurship and stimulate the development of infrastructure for an innovative and digital economy in the country [7].

Economist V.Usoskin paid special attention to improving the quality of loans and cash assets, which are the main types of assets of commercial banks. In order to improve the quality of the loan portfolio, V. Usoskin proposes to improve the system of assessing the creditworthiness of customers, strict adherence to the principle of diversification in the formation of the loan portfolio [8].

N. Sokolinskaya believes that the main focus in asset management and quality improvement should be on their profitability and liquidity [9].

The research of L.G. Batrakova, the nature of interest rate risk in the implementation of deposit policy, assessment, management and the process of establishing a system of measures for insurance are studied [10].

3. Research methodology.

It is known that banks are an integral part of the financial system and operate in close connection with the requirements of the market

and manufacturers. In this regard, the article analyzes the service mechanisms and financial performance of commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

4. Analysis and discussion of results.

In recent years, the country has been trying to increase the range of services provided to its customers and diversify its activities through the development of operations. To this end, banks are actively implementing electronic service technologies such as ATMs, mobile phones and remote management of their accounts via the Internet. Through the implementation of remote banking services, in addition to its traditional operations, the credit institution is also using new banking products that meet the needs of customers more fully and with better quality. But this is not enough, because in the rapidly evolving 21st century information technology age, there are still a number of problems related to real-time banking operations that need to be addressed.

The fact that the “Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 sets the task of further expanding the volume and coverage of cashless payments [11] shows that this issue is still relevant. According to him, a set of measures has been developed to increase the volume and coverage of cashless payments, including the introduction of modern electronic forms of payments in the economy and encourage businesses, as well as reduce off-bank turnover, which include:

- introduction of credit cards, which allow the population to make payments for goods and services at the expense of the bank within a certain period of time;
- Expanding access to remote account service systems (SMS-banking, Internet-banking, banking) through bank plastic cards;

Expanding the ability to manage deposit accounts of individuals through bank plastic cards;

halving the amount of rent for the use of payment terminals;

reduction of tariffs for services for transfer of funds from a plastic card to another card;

In order to stimulate the development of e-commerce, including the simplification of currency and tax control, the introduction of procedures and technologies for refunds for goods and services not received in the system of mutual settlements on plastic cards, commercial banks of the republic to implement these measures a lot of work is being done.

Now let's get acquainted with the systems of remote servicing of bank accounts, remote servicing of accounts - these are the technologies of providing banking services on the basis of remote instructions (without visiting the bank). It is mainly done through computer and telephone networks. There are several types of remote accounts for bank accounts:

Bank-Client is a computer-based system in which a special program is installed on the client's computer. This program stores all customer data on the computer (mainly payment documents and statements from accounts). There is a direct connection between the bank and the client's computer via a modem.

Internet-banking is a system that gives customers the right to manage their deposit accounts, including accounts opened with plastic cards, via the Internet. This type of service is a system designed to make real-time payments when the customer is remotely connected to the bank. The user logs in through a web browser.

The Internet-banking system will be hosted on the bank's web server. The user has the opportunity to view all their information (payment documents and statements from accounts) on the bank's website. Through the

Internet-banking service, the client can do it at his workplace or in other convenient conditions:

transfer of payments;

monitoring of payment stages;

Provides access to all operations at any time, such as receiving all reports.

Through Internet banking, the client will be able to connect to the bank's website from his workplace, see the money coming to his account, prepare money transfers and transfer them to the bank.

Mobile banking system is based on Internet banking technology.

SMS-banking is a bank deposit for customers is a system for receiving information in the form of SMS about transactions on accounts and accounts opened on plastic cards. To get information from the account, the client must send an SMS-request to a special telephone number of the bank.

SMS-banking service for the client allows you to perform the following actions:

funds received on the account;

expenses from the account;

account balance;

will be able to receive operational information on banking operations conducted during the day.

In general, in essence, the difference between traditional and remote banking service schemes of bank and customer communication is not very big.

Both banking services and accounts have remained “in place”, only the type of communication that “connects” the bank employee and customers has changed. That is, transactions that can only be performed in a bank office, now can also be done remotely. The client can “rest on his feet” and not have to waste precious working time on the way to the bank building, claiming that he will perform a minute operation.

Types of remote banking services, such as customer banking, internet, telephone or mobile banking, despite their differences, have

the following common advantages over traditional methods of customer service:

- Improving the quality of service, the time limit will be removed through the remote banking service, ie the customer will be able to

manage their account seven days a week, twenty-four hours a day;

- In addition to time constraints, the customer’s geographical location is also ignored.

Table 1

The number of users of remote banking systems as of April 1, 2022 [12]

№	Banks	Legal entities and individual entrepreneurs	Individuals	The total
1.	National Bank	80 460	1 359 900	1 440 360
2.	Industrial and Construction Bank of Uzbekistan	51 467	2 901 622	2 953 089
3.	Agrobank	172 635	3 346 099	3 518 734
4.	Ipoteka-bank	135 695	1 919 510	2 055 205
5.	Mikrokreditbank	52 619	755 103	807 722
6.	Xalq bank	71 908	3 090 144	3 162 052
7.	Merchant bank	8 636	81 772	90 408
8.	Rural construction bank	24 616	370 100	394 716
9.	Turonbank	29 501	245 870	275 371
10.	Partner bank	98 942	1 300 718	1 399 660
11.	Asaka bank	35 191	923 367	958 558
12.	Silk Road Bank	40 738	1 086 723	1 127 461
13.	Ziraat bank Uzbekistan	2 571	34 526	37 097
14.	Trastbank	34 665	172 011	206 676
15.	Contact bank	45 257	491 330	536 587
16.	KDB Bank Uzbekistan	938	37 780	38 718
17.	Turkistonbank	3 786	15 741	19 527
18.	Soderot bank Toshkent	243	1 793	2 036
19.	Universal bank	8 399	99 127	107 526
20.	Kapitalbank	35 191	353 511	388 702
21.	Ravnaqbank	2 255	46 787	49 042
22.	Davr-bank	22 183	93 773	115 956
23.	Invest Finance bank	24 772	366 885	391 657
24.	Asia Alliance bank	14 888	236 881	251 769
25.	Hi-Tech bank	1 618	22 179	23 797
26.	Orient Finans bank	25 247	365 800	391 047
27.	Madad Invest bank	914	2 531	3 445
28.	Uzagroeksportbank	56	1 286	1 342
29.	Poytaxt bank	851	4 885	5 736
30.	Tenge bank	813	12 783	13 596
31.	TBC bank	0	478 275	478 275
32.	ANOR bank	7 082	801 442	808 524
	The total	1 034 137	21 020 254	22 054 391

The table above shows the number of users of Remote Banking Systems of commercial banks operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan, with 80,460 legal users and

1,359,900 individuals at the expense of the National Bank. The total number of users in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 1,034,137 legal users and 21,020,254 physical users. The total number

of users is 22,054,391. From this we can say that the number of users of banking services in Uzbekistan is growing from year to year, which, along with a sharp increase in demand for banking services, leads to development competition between banks.

It should be noted that the information services of Uzbekistan are developing rapidly, their total volume has increased by 4.6 times. The implementation of programs for the development of telecommunications networks, computerization and information technology is leading to the growth of wireless telephone communications, an increase in the number of mobile subscribers and public access points to the Internet.

5. Conclusions and suggestions.

The bank has 24/7 reception of loan payments of individuals through info kiosks. In carrying out the Bank's operations with depositors, savings books, savings contracts, income and expenditure orders are implemented through an informed program. The launch of the “SMS-deposit” service helps to save time and provide quality services to depositors. The

system of "Biometric identification" using a fingerprint of a person is being introduced in regional branches. In order to further develop the remote services of banks in our country in the future, it is expedient to implement the following we think:

1) introduction of a mechanism for remote transfer of foreign currency transactions (conversion between payment cards in national and foreign currency through mobile applications of banks);

2) to allow the withdrawal of cash foreign currency from conversion payment cards within the country and to expand the network of relevant ATMs.

3) activation of the introduction of innovative banking technologies to create conditions for the provision of modern banking services;

4) increase the culture of the population to trade bank cards electronically;

5) In order to simplify the system of withdrawing cash from ATMs, we believe that the introduction of ATMs in developed countries will be effective in the future.

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